

INFLUENCE OF THE CURING CONDITIONS OF A STRUCTURAL EPOXY FILM ADHESIVE ON THE RESISTANCE TO HYDRAULIC FLUIDS AND THERMAL TRANSITION

S. Lazcano, A. Sánchez, A.T. Rodríguez, J. Sánchez, E. Redondo

**Research and Development, Technology and Materials. Project and Systems Division
Construcciones Aeronáuticas, S.A. (C.A.S.A.). Getafe (Madrid). SPAIN**

ABSTRACT

The influence of processing parameters on the ultimate properties of a 120°C cure epoxy adhesive has been studied. Adhesive samples were cured under several conditions laid within the limits of the generally proposed processing window for the bonding of precured composite laminates with 120°C cure adhesives. Analysis of the obtained glass transition temperatures, thermal stability behaviour, resistance to hydraulic fluids and mechanical properties data (shear strength and peel strength) has been carried out for the differently cured adhesive samples. The results showed poor thermal and chemical resistance behaviour for the specimens cured at the upper temperature limit (135°C).

Keywords: epoxy film adhesive, processing parameters, thermal resistance, chemical resistance, mechanical properties.

1. INTRODUCTION

Adhesive bonding of composites with application in the aircraft industry is a concept which has experienced an increasing interest over the last years¹⁻⁷. The use of polymeric adhesives in a structural application requires a high degree of confidence in the capabilities of the material. There are several factors which can affect, directly or indirectly, the final outcome of the adhesive application. These factors include: adhesive manufacturing batch-to-batch consistency, material age-life history, moisture exposure, application geometry, surface preparation, handling, tooling, lay-up technique and curing (time, temperature, vacuum and pressure)⁸. Among all these factors, curing stands up due to the fact that during this time, the adhesive develops the majority of its foreseen properties. There are three basic factors in the curing of adhesives: time, temperature and pressure. Time and temperature are the components that allow the adhesive to develop the required strength characteristics by chemical reaction, and pressure is responsible for the actual physical configuration of the bond line. Time and temperature, therefore, control the kinetics of the chemical reaction, leading to the polymerization of the resin system.

The aim of this study is to find out the main factor which contributes, and can be controlled, to achieve optimum results. Physical and mechanical measurements can be correlated to chemical changes so that the choice of a cure cycle can be based both on gross resin properties and on molecular structure⁹. There are several techniques that can be used for this purpose. Among them, thermal¹⁰⁻¹³ and mechanical¹⁴⁻¹⁷ properties measurements have been widely applied, and range from simple hardness tests to more complex static mechanical tests or sensitive differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). Differently cured epoxy samples within the selected adhesive processing window (107°C/85 minutes and 135°C/120 minutes) have been analyzed in order to check the influence of the curing parameters on the thermal and chemical resistance behaviour and on the mechanical properties. DSC, TGA and Shore A hardness measurements have been carried out, besides some mechanical tests determination (shear strength and peel strength).

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The 120°C cure epoxy film adhesive selected for this study was FM-73 manufactured by American Cyanamid Company. Two different grades of this modified-epoxy adhesive film with a polyester mat carrier, have been analyzed: FM-73.M.03 (150 g/m²) and FM-73.M.OST.06 (300 g/m²).

2.1. Curing of the adhesive

2.1.1. Adhesive Samples

Three different types of samples have been used:

- Samples cured into the DSC cell
- Panels (4 plies) cured in an autoclave
- Panels (4 plies) cured in an air circulating oven.

Tables 1-3 summarize the experimental conditions applied for each type of curing. These Tables include different heating rates, curing temperatures, curing time and also additional thermal treatment at high temperature (180°C) of some cured FM-73 panels.

Table 1. Curing conditions for FM-73 samples cured into the DSC cell

Condition code	Heating rate from RT to T _c (°C/min)	Curing temperature T _c (°C)	Time at T _c t _c (min)
D1	2	135	100
D21	0.5	120	100
D22	1.5	120	100
D23	2.0	120	100
D24	5.0	120	100
D3	2	107	100

Table 2. Curing conditions for FM-73 samples cured in autoclave (Pressure: 3.2 bars)

Condition code	Heating rate from RT to T _c (°C/min)	Curing temperature T _c (°C)	Time at T _c t _c (min)
A'1	2	135	120
A'2	2	120	90

Table 3. Curing conditions and additional thermal treatments for FM-73 panels cured in an air circulating oven

Condition code	Heating rate from RT to T _c (°C/min)	Curing temperature T _c (°C)	Time at T _c t _c (min)	Additional thermal treatment
O1	2	135	120	---
O11	2	135	120	180°C/90'
O12	2	135	120	180°C/60'
O13	2	135	120	180°C/30'
O2	2	135	85	---
O3	2	107	85	---
O31	2	107	85	180°C/90'
O32	2	107	85	180°C/60'
O33	2	107	85	180°C/30'

2.1.2. Mechanical tests specimens

2.1.2.1. Shear tests

Metal bonded panels were prepared in an autoclave (pressure: 3.2 bars) under the curing conditions shown in Table 4. Cladded aluminium alloy 2024-T3 panels with a surface preparation consisting of sulfochromic pickling, chromic anodizing and BR-127 primer were used. The dimensions of the test specimens are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Shear tests: specimens dimensions

Table 4. Curing conditions and additional thermal treatments for the shear tests panels

Condition code	Heating rate from RT to T_c ($^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$)	Curing temperature T_c ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Time at T_c t_c (min)	Additional thermal treatment
A1	2	135	120	---
A11	2	135	120	120 $^{\circ}\text{C}/90'$ (5 cycles)
A12	2	135	120	180 $^{\circ}\text{C}/90'$
A2	2	120	90	---
A21	2	120	90	120 $^{\circ}\text{C}/90'$ (5 cycles)
A3	2	107	85	---
A31	2	107	85	120 $^{\circ}\text{C}/90'$ (5 cycles)
A32	2	107	85	180 $^{\circ}\text{C}/90'$

2.1.2.2 Peel tests

Metal/metal (Bell) peeling tests specimens were autoclave cured (pressure: 3.2 bars) under the conditions shown in Table 5. Cladded aluminium alloy 2024-T3 panels with identical surface preparation as mentioned in paragraph 2.1.2.1 were prepared. The dimensions of the test specimens are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Peel tests: specimens dimensions

Table 5. Curing conditions for the peel tests panels

Condition code	Heating rate from RT to T_c ($^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$)	Curing Temperature T_c ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Time at T_c t_c (min)
A1	2	135	120
A2	2	120	90
A3	2	107	85

2.2. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

DSC measurements were carried out in a Perkin-Elmer Differential Scanning Calorimeter DSC-7, using sample weights of 7-10 mg. This technique was used in order to cure FM-73 samples under different conditions (see Table 1) and, also, to determine the glass transition temperature of cured adhesive samples (heating rate: 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$)

2.3. Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA)

TGA tests were carried out using a Perkin-Elmer Thermogravimetric Analyzer TGA-7. All the tests were conducted under nitrogen atmosphere, in a temperature range from 50 to 850°C and at a heating rate of 20°C/min.

2.4. Chemical resistance studies

The chemical resistance behaviour was checked after conditioning of differently cured adhesive samples and mechanical tests specimens. The conditioning was carried out by immersion in hydraulic fluid (Chevron Hyjet IV) or mixtures hydraulic fluid: H₂O at different temperatures. For the Shore A hardness measurements, ten determinations per specimen were performed.

2.5. Mechanical tests

2.5.1. Shear Tests

Shear tests were performed at room temperature, at a rate of 1 mm/min and five specimens were tested per type of condition.

2.5.2. Peel Tests

Peel tests were performed at room temperature, at a rate of 100 mm/min, using rollers of 25 mm diameter. Five specimens were tested per type of condition.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Influence of the curing conditions on the glass transition temperature (T_g) of FM-73

The obtained glass transition temperatures of differently cured adhesive samples measured by DSC are shown in Tables 6 and 7. These Tables show the influence of the processing parameters (time, temperature and pressure) and contain the T_g of samples cured into the DSC cell, as well as samples cured in an oven and samples taken from tested shear tests specimens (cured in autoclave).

Table 6. Influence of the curing temperature (T_c) and stabilization time (t_c) on the T_g of FM-73 (heating rate = 2°C/min).

Condition code	T_c (°C)	t_c (min)	T_g (°C)
O1	135	120	94
A1		120	95
D1		100	91
O2		85	93
D23	120	100	104
D3	107	100	101
O3		85	113
A3		85	105

Table 7. Influence of the heating rate on the T_g of FM-73 (stabilization time, t_c = 100 min)

Condition code	Heating rate (°C/min)	T_c (°C)	T_g (°C)
D21	0.5	120	105
D22	1.5		105
D23	2.0		104
D24	5.0		104

Table 8. Influence of the additional thermal treatment on the T_g of FM-73

Condition code	T_c (°C)	Additional thermal treatment	T_g (°C)
O11	135	180 °C/90'	95
O12		180 °C/60'	99
O13		180 °C/30'	101
A11		120 °C/90' (5 cycles)	98
A21	120	120 °C/90' (5 cycles)	98
O31	107	180 °C/90'	104
O32		180 °C/60'	104
O33		180 °C/30'	103
A31		120 °C/90' (5 cycles)	99

The results show that the curing temperature is the major factor which controls the T_g of the material, being the influence of the heating rate and curing time negligible in the analyzed processing window (see Figures 3 and 4). The main conclusion which arises from these results is that, surprisingly, lower T_g values are obtained when samples are cured at the upper limit of the processing window (135°C).

On the other hand, additional thermal treatment of any of the differently cured samples tend to level the measured T_g , as shown in Table 8. Finally, a general good agreement between samples cured into the DSC cell (D), in an oven (O) and in autoclave (A) should be also mentioned.

Figure 3. DSC curves obtained for FM-73 cured at different curing temperatures

Figure 4. DSC curves obtained for FM-73 cured at different heating rates

3.2. Influence of the curing conditions on the thermal resistance behaviour of FM-73

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was used to study the degradation behaviour of differently cured FM-73 samples. The temperature at which the onset of the degradation occurs (T_{onset}) was determined as shown in Figure 5 and results are summarized in Table 9.

This Table includes the analysis of samples cured in an oven at different curing temperatures and subjected to several additional thermal treatments. The analysis of samples taken from tested shear specimens is also included (conditions A11, A21 and A31). The results show the same trend already described for the T_g variation (paragraph 3.1.), i.e., lower thermal stability behaviour (lower T_{onset}) for the samples cured at the upper temperature (135°C). Additional thermal treatment of any of the cured samples doesn't lead to a degradation of the material.

Figure 5. TGA curves obtained for FM-73 cured at (--) 135°C/120 min and (- -) 107°C/85 min

3.3. Influence of the curing conditions on the chemical resistance of FM-73

3.3.1. Shore A hardness measurements

The influence of the curing temperature on the chemical resistance behaviour of differently cured FM-73 samples was assessed by measuring the Shore A hardness. The values obtained for samples cured at different temperatures (conditions A'1 and A'2) showed no influence of the curing conditions on the results. However, after 14 days of immersion at RT in hydraulic fluid or hydraulic fluid: H₂O mixtures, an average of 96% retention of the hardness values for 135°C cured samples was found versus a 98% retention for 120°C cured samples.

This behaviour was confirmed by the results obtained after immersion at 70°C as it can be observed in Figures 6 and 7. The curves show, in general, a better solvent resistance behaviour for samples cured at the lower temperature, even for the samples subjected to additional thermal treatment.

Table 9. TGA results for differently cured FM-73 samples

Condition code	T _c (°C)	Additional thermal treatment	T _{onset} (°C)
O1	135		426
O2			423
O3	107		436
O11	135	180 °C/90'	429
O12		180 °C/60'	428
O13		180 °C/30'	432
A11		120 °C/90' (5 cycles)	426
A21	120	120 °C/90' (5 cycles)	434
O31	107	180 °C/90'	436
O32		180 °C/60'	453
O33		180 °C/30'	447
A31		120 °C/90' (5 cycles)	435

The effect of this treatment on the chemical resistance behaviour of the samples, was found to be negligible for specimens cured at 135°C (conditions O1 and O11). However, for specimens cured at 107°C (conditions O3 and O31), similar Shore A hardness values were reached, but at shorter immersion times for condition O31.

Figure 6. Variation of the Shore A hardness after immersion of the specimens in Hydraulic fluid at 70°C. a) Specimens cured at 135°C. b) Specimens cured at 107°C.

Figure 7. Variation of the Shore A hardness after immersion of the specimens in Hydraulic fluid: H₂O (50:50) at 70°C. a) Specimens cured at 135°C. b) Specimens cured at 107°C.

3.3.2. Mechanical tests

Shear strength and peel strength values were also determined and the results (Table 10) also showed poorer chemical resistance for the specimens cured at the upper temperature. Shear tests values obtained after different immersion times (7 and 40 days) suggest that saturation of mechanical specimens is reached at shorter times than saturation of Shore A hardness specimens. Moreover, the higher % retention of mechanical properties compared with the more dramatic decrease found for the Shore A hardness values, can be easily explained due to the minimal exposure of the adhesive to the hydraulic fluid for the mechanical tests specimen configuration.

Table 10. % retention of shear and peel strength values for conditioned specimens cured at different temperatures.

Condition code	T _c (°C)	Conditioning	Shear Strength (% retention)	Peel Strength (% retention)
A1	135	7 days immersion in hydraulic fluid at 70°C	77	84
A3	107		83	91
A1	135	40 days immersion in hydraulic fluid at 70°C	76	--
A2	120		79	--
A3	107		82	--
A1	135	7 days immersion in hydraulic fluid:H ₂ O (70:30) at 70°C	71	87
A3	107		83	90

3.4. Influence of the curing conditions on the mechanical properties of FM-73

This study has been completed by analyzing if the cure temperature influences the mechanical behaviour of the adhesive. The obtained average results (Table 11) show no influence of the curing conditions or additional thermal treatment on the shear strength values. However, higher peel strength data are obtained for the specimens cured at 135°C, which can be correlated with the already mentioned lower glass transition temperatures and may indicate a lower crosslink density.

Table 11. Shear strength and peel strength results for FM-73 specimens cured at different temperatures

Condition code	T _c (°C)	Additional thermal treatment	Shear Strength (MPa)		Peel Strength (N)	
			Average	(S)	Average	(S)
A1	135		37.6	0.3	228	5
A2	120		38.9	1.2	218	13
A3	107		38.4	0.9	183	4
A11	135	120°C/90' (5 cycles)	38.4	0.8	--	--
A12		180°C/90'	38.0	1.0	--	--
A21	120	120°C/90' (5 cycles)	38.1	1.1	--	--
A31	107	120°C/90' (5 cycles)	38.0	2.1	--	--
A32		180°C/90'	36.6	1.8	--	--

4. CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study have shown that temperature is the main processing parameter which needs to be controlled during the curing of this epoxy film adhesive in order to achieve optimum properties. The other processing parameters (heating rate, stabilization time and pressure) have been shown to have no significant incidence on the final properties of the adhesive when the material is cured inside the analyzed processing window (107°C/85 min - 135°C/120 min).

The curing of the adhesive at the upper temperature limit (135°C) produces a decrease in the glass transition temperature and a diminution of the thermal and chemical resistance behaviour of the cured system, as well as higher peel strength values although it has no influence on the shear strength results. Additional thermal treatment of any of the differently cured samples has a negligible effect on the thermal (T_g) and mechanical (shear strength) properties, although it seems to speed up the chemical attack process by the phosphoric ester based hydraulic fluid.

REFERENCES

- 1.- Rienhart T.J., *Evolution of Structural Adhesives*, SAMPE Conference on Adhesive Bonding. Los Angeles, CA 1982.
- 2.- Hart-Smith L.J., *Adhesively Bonded Joints for Fibrous Composite Structures*, Joining Fibre-reinforced Plastics, Edited by F.L. Matthews, Elsevier Applied Science Publishers, Ltd., Essex, England 1987, pp. 271-311.
- 3.- Cagle C.V., *Adhesive Bonding*, Mc Graw-Hill, 1968
- 4.- Matthews F.L., Kilty P.F. and Godwin E.W., *A Review of the Strength of Joints in Fibre-reinforced Plastics. Part 2. Adhesively Bonded Joints*, Composites, Vol. 13, January 1982, pp. 29-37.
- 5.- Hart-Smith L.J., *Further Developments in Design and Analysis of Adhesive-Bonded Structural Joints*, Joining of Composite Materials, STP 749, K.T. Kedward Ed., 1981, pp. 3-31.
- 6.- Nageswara Rao B., Sadasiva Rao Y.V.K. and Yadagiri, S., *Analysis of Composite Bonded Joints*, Fibre Science and Technology, 17, 1982, pp. 77-90.
- 7.- Pocius A.V., Wenz R.P., *Mechanical Surface Preparation of Graphite-Epoxy Composite for Adhesive Bonding*, Proceedings of 30th National SAMPE Symposium, March 1985, pp. 1073-1087.
- 8.- Roberts R.W., *Processing Quality Control*, Engineered Materials Handbook, Vol. 3, ASM International, U.S.A. 1990, pp. 735-742.
- 9.- Ochi M., Tanaka Y. and Shimbo M., *Curing Mechanism of Epoxy Resin*, Nippon Kagaku Kaishi 9, 1600 (1975).
- 10.- Wendtland W.W., *Thermal Methods of Analysis*, 2nd ed., J. Wiley and Sons, N.Y., U.S.A. 1974.
- 11.- Fava R., *Differential Scanning Calorimetry of Epoxy Resins*, Polymer 9, 137 (1968).
- 12.- Carpenter J.F. and Bartels T.T., *Characterization and Control of Composite Prepregs and Adhesives*, Proceedings of the 7th National SAMPE Technical Conference, Albuquerque, New Mexico, Vol. 7, October 1975, p. 43.
- 13.- May C.A., Whearty D.K. and Fritzen J.S., *Composite Cure Studies by Dielectric and Calorimetric Analyses*, Proceedings of the 21st National SAMPE Symposium, Los Angeles, C.A., Vol. 21, April 1976, p. 803.
- 14.- Kaelble D.H., *Dynamic and Tensile Properties of Epoxy Resins*, J. Appl. Polym. Sci. 9, 1213 (1965).
- 15.- Chiao T.T., Cummins A.D. and Moore R.L., *Fabrication and Testing of Epoxy Tensile Specimens*, Composites 3, 10 (1972).
- 16.- Selby K. and Miller L., *Fracture Toughness and Mechanical Behaviour of an Epoxy Resin*, J. Mater. Sci. 10, 12 (1975).
- 17.- Arridge R. and Speake J., *Mechanical Relaxation Studies of the Cure of Epoxy Resins: 1. Measurement of Cure*, Polymer 13, 443 (1972).